

Information and consent form

Information sheet

Name of Principal Investigator:	Lore Van Praag
Organisation:	XXX
Name of Funding organisation:	Horizon Europe RIA
Project Title and Version:	ReIncluGen: Rethinking Inclusion and Gender empowerment A participatory action research

Introduction

I am [researcher] of [organisation]. I am part of the ReIncluGen project, which is a participatory research that aims to unpack the different conceptualisations of gender empowerment from a 'situated intersectional' approach and evaluate empowering and inclusive practices of European civil society organisations, and how these are embedded in policies and media discourses in order to co-design a digital networking platform and other innovative tools to further support these CSOs.

In this information letter, I would like to give you more information about the topic of this research project and the purpose of this study. I would like to invite you to be part of this research. This consent form may contain words that you do not understand. Please ask me for explanations when anything is unclear, in this letter or during the research.

Purpose of the research

The ReIncluGen project aims to study and co-construct creative and innovative ways to help reverse socio-economic and cultural inequalities and help realise gender empowerment and inclusion of migrant women and girls across societal, cultural and economic contexts in Europe. In order to realise this the project aims to rethink and move beyond gender empowerment as a container term. In doing so, ReIncluGen will consider a more critical and holistic approach of empowerment that aims to rethink and re-imagine gender empowerment as a process, with different manifestations depending on the socio-political context, rather than as a loosely articulated outcome. By researching the various concepts of gender empowerment that are present, as well as the discourses in digital media, we will automatically also touch on issues of structural violence. Focusing on the target group of migrant women and girls and the diversity and agency within this group is of particular relevance which leads us to approach gender empowerment as interrelated to issues of gender, class and race. As a consortium, we strongly support the right to movement and migration of every person. Despite the potential for this right to migration to improve women's lives, we are aware of the many disadvantages and risks that women face as compared to men. Moreover, our focus on migrant women and girls will bring along different meanings and understandings of gender empowerment that will challenge liberal and Western notions of freedom and empowerment on which many policy initiatives and policies are built in a paternalistic way to 'empower' or 'save' female migrants.

The first objective of the ReIncluGen project is to use a bottom-up and participatory approach to unpack the different meanings of gender 'empowerment' across societal spheres and contexts. A second objective is to evaluate the empowering and inclusive work and impact of CSOs in order to further support them in their (digital) needs. A third objective is to examine the discourses and actions of media and digital cultures in strengthening, supporting or contributing to gender empowerment. In doing so, we aim to understand the impact of these media discourses on the used CSO practices and vice versa.

Participant selection

You are being invited to take part in this research because I feel that your experience as a person who has worked on gender empowerment or as a person with interesting insights on gender empowerment could help researchers and policy makers to better understand how people interpret gender empowerment and how they apply it in their everyday lives and professional activities.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary. It is your choice whether to participate or not. The choice that you make will have no bearing on your job or on any work-related evaluations or reports. You may change your mind later and stop participating even if you agreed earlier.

Right to Withdraw

You have the right to withdraw your consent to use the personal data that you have provided at any time (unless the data has been anonymized). You do not have to justify your decision to withdraw your consent and there are no consequences for withdrawing your consent.

Type of research intervention and procedures

The research takes place over 36 months in total. During that time, we will ask you to participate in an interview, focus group discussion, which lasts about 1-1,5 hours and 1,5-2 hours respectively. The researcher may ask to participate in one or more interviews/focus group discussions. If you are interested, I will additionally you to take photos that defines gender empowerment for you.

During this interview/focus group discussion, we will ask you some questions about how you define gender empowerment and how do you think its needs to be supported. There are no good or wrong answers. If you do not wish to answer any of the questions during the interview, you may say so and the interviewer will move on to the next question. The entire interview/focus group discussion will be tape-recorded. We will not mention your name in the interview. All interviews will pseudonymised.

Potential Risks and Discomforts

During the interview/focus group discussions, personal questions will be asked regarding some profound events that happened to you. This may evoke memories and emotions. In case you need emotional support and a listening ear, you can contact [local victim support organisation and contact details per country].

Potential Benefits

There will be no direct benefit to you, but your participation is likely to help us find out more about to reflect on gender empowerment, within and across civil society organisations.

Privacy

During this research I will ask you to provide personal data, such as your birthplace, age, gender, religion, languages you speak and profession. This way, we can better understand whether these factors play or do not play a role for your views on climate change and how this differs when compared to other participants. We will process the information in such way that you cannot be identified by others.

As indicated above, this research project involves making audio recordings of interviews with you. The audio recordings will be transcribed (that is, put into writing). Segments of the transcribed interview may be used in published forms (for example, journal articles and book chapters). The segment will never directly or indirectly identify you as a person; the segments used are anonymous.

Confidentiality

- I will only share your personal data with people who are directly involved in this research. In case of job students, a non-disclosure agreement will be signed.

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- Your name and contact details are kept separately and afterwards removed from your answers as soon as possible. They will be replaced with a fake number.
- I have designed the questions in such a way that your answers will not directly or indirectly identify you.

Retaining and Sharing your data

- Your personal data (for example, audio or video recordings, forms, and other documents created or collected as part of this study) will be stored in a secure location for a minimum period of 10 years after the results of the research have been published to give other researchers the opportunity to check if the research is done properly.

Sharing the Results

I will share the knowledge that I get from this research with you and your community before I will make it widely available to the public.

Your Privacy Rights and Contact Information

You have the right to request access to your personal data and to change these if they are not right or to erase your data. If you want to invoke your rights or if you have a question concerning privacy about this study, you can contact Erasmus University's DPO (Data Protection Officer) at fg@eur.nl. If you would like to lodge a complaint concerning privacy, you can do this with the national supervisory authority in the Netherlands on personal data (Autoriteit Persoonsgegevens).

Who to Contact

If you have any questions, you can ask them now or later. If you wish to ask questions later, you may contact any of the following: Lore Van Praag, 0616103593, vanpraag@essb.eur.nl

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Certificate of consent

I have read the Informed Consent Form and I understand what the purpose of the research is and that data will be collected from me. The research has been explained to me clearly and I have been able to ask questions.

By signing this Form, I

1. consent to participate in this research.
2. confirm that I am at least 18 years old.
3. understand that participating in this research is completely voluntary; and
4. understand that my data will be anonymised for publication, educational purposes and further research, unless I give my consent to the Quotes and/or Photos and/or Education and further research options below.

Consent Special categories of personal data

I give my consent to the collection, processing, use and storage of my personal data for the purposes of this research including data related to race/ethnic origin/religious beliefs/migrant experience and trajectory.

Audio/Video

I hereby consent to having audio and/or video recordings made during the research and to have my answers transcribed.

Quotes

I hereby consent to having my answers quoted in research publications. When quotes are used, your (real) name and other direct identifiers will not be mentioned.

Education and further Research

I hereby consent to having my personal data, namely the anonymized and pseudonymized data stored and used for educational purposes and for future research, also in other areas of research than this research.

Photos

I give permission to be show my photos for research purposes. I retain the copyright of my photos.

New research

I give permission to be contacted again for new research.

Name of the participant:

Signature of the participant:

Date:

